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Missing links: Understanding blindness to safety risks

ESReDA Project Group *Risk, Knowledge, Management*

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Preface

This document is the result of a joint effort by members of the ESReDA project group on *Risk, Knowledge and Management*. They are experts from different European countries who work in different roles related to safety management, from firms in different industry sectors, consultancies, safety authorities, and research and development organizations. The document aims to provide useful information, from both theoretical and practical viewpoints, about the intersection between risk management, knowledge management and decision-making concerning safety issues, based on current practices and the state of scientific knowledge.

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The project group would like to thank participants in the two ESReDA seminars organized by the group:

- the 65th seminar *From risk imagination to safety intervention - Managing risks with knowledge* organized in Athens in November 2024, where the interactive session that led to the present document was held (the proceedings are [available online](#));
- the 58th seminar *Using Knowledge to Manage Risks and Threats: Practices and Challenges*, organized online in June 2021 (the proceedings are [available online](#)).

The European Safety, Reliability and Data Association (ESReDA) was created in 1992 as a forum for sharing knowledge on the safety and reliability of industrial processes and critical infrastructures. It facilitates cooperation between experts from different countries and different industry sectors, safety authorities, expertise organisations and academic organisations. ESReDA is a non-profit association which hosts project groups on specific topics, and organises biannual seminars on topics of interest to its members.

The project group contributors thank ESReDA member organisations for support of the meetings that allowed the production of this document.

Executive summary

This executive summary is an output from the interactive session organised by the ESReDA project group on *Risk, Knowledge and Management* at the ESReDA seminar held in Athens in November 2024. The seminar included a poster session with four posters, each with a claim concerning organisational blindness to safety risks. As part of the seminar, the audience was divided into four groups, and each group was asked to spend 20 minutes with a poster, then move on to the next one. At the poster, the audience was given a short presentation of the claim on the poster, and the background to it, and asked about their thoughts concerning the claim.

The objective of this summary is to thank the audience for their participation, and to give all participants a reminder of what the posters claimed, feedback on what was discussed in the interactive sessions, and information on what conclusions were then made. This executive summary does not claim to be the truth, but instead we hope it rouses thoughts and ideas on potential ways to reduce organisational blindness, better identify safety problems and ensure that the decisions required to reduce risks are not buried by the myriad of other pressures that affect every organisation.

The posters addressed different facets of organisational (and organised) blindness: (1) how complexity contributes to the blindness of organisations, (2) how you can be wilfully blind, (3) how to detect that you may be blind to issues, and (4) how you can tackle blindness with smarter communication. The discussions helped identify concepts and practices that can help reinforce the link that should exist between knowledge of threats to safety and the allocation of organisational resources to prevent accidents.

The **first poster** was about the dissemination of responsibility in complex systems in which people belonging to multiple organisations have to collaborate and coordinate to make decisions about safety management. In such systems, awareness concerning risks tends to be distributed, and accountability for safety

is spread across several people and therefore weakened. We see this across multiple accidents including the Key Bridge accident (Baltimore, 2024), the Deepwater Horizon catastrophe, and the Grenfell Tower fire. These complex organisational structures are becoming increasingly common for multi-stakeholder systems and infrastructures, so we need to be aware of the associated challenges.

Several points were raised by the audience of the Athens seminar: First of all, this may often be seen in particular in systems which involve public and private partnership, and in which multiple stakeholders need to participate in the system governance. A “pass-the-buck” phenomenon is often seen when investigating accidents in such systems. Second, a strong regulatory framework can help avoid certain problems which appear with these complex organisational structures, but the strength of the regulatory system is very variable depending on the industry sector concerned. It is necessary to find effective collaboration and decision-making mechanisms despite the presence of silos, and despite diverging interests from stakeholders. Finally, the participants pointed out that monolithic systems are not immune to these challenges because obstacles to information sharing and to clear accountability are also present inside systems run by a single organisation.

The **second poster** claimed that needed upgrades to engineering are sometimes stopped by wilful blindness. The participants agreed on that, noting a lack of strategies to deal with it. Wilful blindness was, however, expected to be more likely in some settings than others. The optimism of small business owners can be seen as an exercise in wilful blindness. Several participants pointed out that, beyond the usual adage “if it ain’t broke, don’t fix it”, the IT sector tightly embraces a culture of “if it works, don’t touch it” and “it’s good enough”. Hence, even if the client is mindful of risks, an overly pragmatic software development team might not be.

Our participants also noted that wilful blindness seems to be at work in discussions of reasonable practicability. These included: how experts are selected, how good practice is determined, how standard-setting bodies are governed, and how risks themselves are (subsequently) framed. Foresight, one participant noted, gets worse gradually and is not easily restored. The concept of ethical fading implies a similar incrementalism. A participant noted that this dynamic has a social inertia. In practice, a group that migrates in increments to a new deviant norm is very reluctant to reverse its steps.

A “don’t ask, don’t tell” culture is hard to undo once embedded. Stakeholder engagement, we would expect, should help to reduce wilful blindness, making it less likely or more easily countered. Likewise, if the relationships between the

employer and the workforce are poor, as one of our participants noted, it can be hard for a manager to distinguish between valid concerns and the flexing of an agenda.

One of the participants spoke of his disappointment to find, on returning to his country after twenty years away, that some problems were unchanged. It was noted that, when one level of government is challenged, they are adept at blaming the level above. Wilful blindness can create its own metarisk of fueling mistrust in institutions and wider political processes.

The **third poster** was about early warning signs. We propose that detecting and acting on EWS are very important to get both knowledge management and risk management to a higher level of efficiency and effectiveness. Starting from the notion that an EWS is early, and warns of escalation, we build on past experience that if the EWS is not acted on, the disturbance-scenario will escalate and have a bigger impact leading up to a major accident. Therefore, the solution is to stop this escalation as soon as possible by detecting EWS and acting upon them with knowledge-based and evidence-based risk management. The main approach is to identify the components of the normal/abnormal flow which starts with an observation of reality and which — after e.g. data analysis, interpretation, information, knowledge, and decision-making — should end with an action on that reality.

To progress to a solution it is very important to learn the boundaries of the safe region of operation, and that transgressing the boundaries is in fact an early warning sign that should prompt action. For example, the Key Bridge accident included several early warning signs — elements that were known concerning both the status of the bridge and the situation on the vessel — examples which were used to kick off discussion with the interactive session participants.

The insights gained in from this interaction included that promoting diversity in teams (including shop-floor workers) is essential to support the interpretation of signals; that information overload can hide the critical information; that fostering a culture of feedback and learning is critical; that if the data is partial, incomplete, or influenced by biases, the conclusions drawn from it may be misleading, hindering the ability to detect warning signs.

The **fourth poster** was about communication: are accidents due to bad communication of the risk that is understood by the safety professional but not by the decision-maker who remains blind to it? How should the available knowledge be communicated so that it leads to the decision-maker both understanding the

issues and acting upon them? Complex matters may lead to decision-makers focusing on only their own field of expertise and omitting the rest, or the decision-maker may already have decided and is not motivated to change.

According to the seminar discussions with the audience, smart communication is about defining what is the content, objective, and best method and timing of the communication, what evidence should be used, and identifying who should communicate to whom: to drive change, safety professionals should tailor the message to match the perception and judgement capabilities of the audience. At the same time, both the person sharing the information and the person receiving it need to understand that it takes effort to shift beliefs and gain understanding.

In conclusion, as key takeaways from the interactive session of the seminar, we now understand that we can treat corporations as entities, and individuals as entities, but we cannot treat a team or the system as an entity. When discussing blindness, we pick on individuals even though it is a team function, and could even be a corporate function. When everyone is responsible, no one is responsible. How organisations are organised internally for accountability, is important. Here, the framework to regulate how stakeholders engage and collaborate is of importance to help organisations “do governance” and gain foresight.

Blindness can involve bad behaviour but usually the behaviour is within the normal range, but with a bad consequence. Perhaps this is a subject which like others is a matter of fitting the task to the person. Do we need to design our processes to more closely fit how people are, how they work together? Still, people are really reluctant to talk about blindness. Why: fear; denial? This has made the problem more or less undiscussable. We need to recognise that there are some rule sets that are lacking in the workplace. And sometimes a decision has to be made to slow down, think, and make more deliberate choices.

In the scope of blindness, early warning signs are an important element. Signals need to be identified and managed, not suppressed. Here, early warning signs are identifiable only if networks function: for example, by trouble-free collaboration between stakeholders, which would avoid signals being lost. We need something where early warning signs are talked about and acted upon. This does not happen sometimes, maybe because the decision-making process is unwieldy. Here, a more agile process might be the answer, to avoid shortcuts and the blindness that comes with it.

There are ways to communicate that actually create blindness. Your message is also competing with other messages, and we probably do not think about communication as much as we should. You can always blame “poor” communication after the fact, and you would be right, but that is not helpful. You need

to think more concretely about the way you are communicating: you need to think strategically to get the best possible chance to gain results that make the difference in safety.

The poster sessions, and reflections since, make it clear that blindness is an issue to which we lack answers. However, blindness is usually discussed only in hindsight, and surrounded by negative emotions and recrimination. In the workplace, blindness is feared for its punishing consequences. To make progress, the subject first needs to be brought to light and made discussable.

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Introduction

This document's objectives

Knowledge-based and ethical risk management have “critical” conditions that make the difference between success and failure. These conditions enable technical approaches to supply information and apply knowledge to actual decisions about risks. However, various issues, mostly non-technical, decide whether these conditions are met or undermined.

Often after major accidents we realise that:

- knowledge of the hazard was available;
- potential risk prevention or mitigation measures had been identified;
- the necessary decisions had not been made.

There often seems to be a missing link between knowledge and action. This paper discusses possible causes for this, focusing on the notion of **organisational blindness**. Clarity about these issues will allow practitioners and theorists to develop ways to resolve or avoid them, leading to better management of risks.

In this paper, we attempt to:

- explain what the issues are and how they are manifest;
- set out the principles that individuals use to address these issues (those present and those needed but missing), and give practical examples;
- reflect on the topics raised in Athens.

The objective of the paper is to rouse thoughts on how to reduce organisational blindness, to better identify safety problems and to ensure that the decisions to reduce risks are not buried under the myriad other pressures that affect every organisation.

The paper is the output from an interactive session organised by the ESReDA project group on Risk, Knowledge and Management at the ESReDA seminar held

in Athens in November 2024. It provides some background information concerning the claims presented during the interactive session and summarises the points discussed with the participants of the interactive session.

The paper does not claim to be scientific or all-encompassing, nor are the claims and ideas presented here meant to be the whole truth. Credit as main author of each subchapter is given to the presenters of the four posters, with extra thanks given to their rapporteurs for input and support, and all other project group members for their additional thoughts, discussion, and both converging and diverging opinions that provoked fruitful discussions.

Structure of this document

Chapter 1 provides some context to the content of the paper. We describe the volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous world in which many high-consequence systems and infrastructures are embedded. The 2024 collapse of the Francis Scott Key Bridge in Baltimore, USA, which is used as a case study in the document, is briefly described. The concept of organisational blindness which we develop in the rest of the paper is outlined.

Chapter 2 claims that organisational complexity and the diffusion of responsibility for safety makes accidents almost inevitable in the long term. This is due to the phenomenon of dissemination of responsibility for ensuring safety across multiple organisations and individuals; the lack of resources, decision-making authority and perceived legitimacy to implement significant changes; and the inevitable drift toward danger that affects complex multistakeholder systems.

Chapter 3 claims that wilful blindness, the deliberate or subconscious omission of relevant knowledge from a decision, stops needed engineering upgrades. In other words, there are occasions when decision-makers remove, avoid, or distort key data that would otherwise commit their organisation to making a costly, inconvenient change. The authors argue that the challenges to improved decision-making are not purely technocratic, but social also. A number of behaviours and conditions that make wilful blindness more likely are presented.

Chapter 4 defends the claim that major accidents often occur because of a system's inability to recognise and respond effectively to various (early) warning signs that arise during its functioning. The presence of early warning signs of accidental situations implies an obligation to ensure the organisation is alert to these events, to analyze them when they are detected, and to implement changes if the analysis shows that they are necessary. This proactive management activity strengthens the link between risk, knowledge and management.

Chapter 5 claims that poor communication by safety professionals can leave managers blind to risks that need action. The authors note that communication is a specific skill, that gaining understanding and shifting beliefs is effortful activity, and that sharing knowledge is not the same as learning from knowledge.

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Background

This paper views blindness to risk against the background of global change. The interactive sessions from which this paper arose used the 2024 collapse of the Francis Scott Key Bridge as a case study. In part, the collapse is the story of an old design outpaced by change; the growing tonnage of ships. The biggest container ships in 2024 carry eight times as many containers as ships could when the bridge opened in 1978 [Allyn International 2024]. That is just one instance of global change that provides the general context for this paper: blindness is becoming more likely and more consequential as the world becomes ever more volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous.

1.1 In a VUCA world

Organisations operate in what can be described as a VUCA (Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, Ambiguous) world [Bennett and Lemoine 2014]. Rapid changes in technology, geopolitics, economics, and societal trends can quickly outpace traditional risk management and decision-making approaches. This environment increases the likelihood of blindness to safety risks, as organisations must be agile, adaptive, and resilient in how they acquire, process, and act upon knowledge.

Today's global trends add further layers of complexity. Systems are not only larger and more internationally interconnected than 30 years ago, but they also face unprecedented pressures from technological advancements, environmental constraints, and shifting global standards. As we build ever more complex systems, knowledge management becomes more challenging, making it critical to break down long-standing silos and rethink conventional approaches to risk management [Founders Workshop 2024].

In such a volatile environment, knowledge silos become particularly risky. The interconnected nature of global issues means that effective risk management requires cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration. However, integrating insights from diverse fields — each with its own terminology, methodologies, and

concerns — poses considerable challenges. Furthermore, leadership today is increasingly characterised by a detachment from day-to-day operations [Souarez 2018]. Leaders often face tradeoffs between short-term gains and long-term safety investments, and may prioritise strategic image or external perceptions over robust risk management. For instance, they might opt for cost-cutting measures that compromise safety protocols or delay critical maintenance to meet immediate financial targets. This trade-off can leave the practitioners on the ground without the support or authority to address systemic problems, further contributing to blindness to safety risks.

At the same time, leadership dynamics have evolved. Today's leaders and politicians are often less hands-on and increasingly distant from day-to-day operations. Effective leaders can foster sensemaking practices that help teams interpret complex data and anticipate risks. They can also empower decision-making at lower levels, allowing those directly involved in managing critical systems to respond quickly to emerging issues. However, poor leadership can exacerbate risks by failing to provide clear decision-making frameworks or adequate resources for risk mitigation. In many cases, they prioritise strategic image or short-term gains — sometimes at the cost of deeper accountability — effectively doing the best they can with the resources available. This trade-off means that while leadership remains critical, the people doing the work are frequently left without the power or democratic mechanisms needed to correct systemic issues or remove underperforming leadership. In both positive and negative scenarios, the quality of leadership directly impacts the organisation's ability to manage risks effectively and avoid blindness to safety risks.

Innovative approaches to knowledge management are emerging as a response. Effective knowledge systems should harness data, experience, and insights from across the organisation, turning information into actionable knowledge. This process involves breaking down silos, fostering cross-functional/cross-sectoral collaboration, and using technologies like AI and data analytics to detect early warning signs.

The modern workplace also demands a rethinking of lifelong learning. In today's work environment, learning is often unstructured and driven by problem-solving in real time. Organisations must cultivate agile individuals who are capable of evolving with the world — and who, in turn, demand more from their leaders. They must deal with questions such as: How can we ensure our knowledge bases remain relevant when the context changes so quickly? What strategies can we employ to capture and disseminate critical insights in real-time? How do we balance the need for stable, reliable information with the imperative to adapt to new realities? And how do we cultivate leadership that is both accountable

and proactive in an environment where decision-makers are frequently far away from the operational challenges their teams face?

Ultimately, the organisations that will thrive in this VUCA world will be those that can transform their knowledge systems from static repositories into dynamic, evolving ecosystems. These systems must not only keep pace with change but anticipate it, turning the challenges of a VUCA environment into opportunities for growth and resilience. Organisations that effectively integrate knowledge and risk management, and embrace the demands for improved leadership and lifelong learning, remaining connected and responsible, will be better equipped to navigate the multifaceted challenges and complexities of our time, especially in the realm of critical infrastructure safety, thereby reducing the risk of blindness to safety risks.

1.2 The Francis Scott Key Bridge collapse (Baltimore, 2024)

In March 2024, an electrical failure on the container ship Dali led to its collision with one of the piers of the Francis Scott Key Bridge in Baltimore, USA, leading to the collapse of the bridge. Six members of a maintenance crew working on the roadway were killed, while two more were rescued from the river. The collapse blocked most shipping to and from the Port of Baltimore for 11 weeks. Insurance claims related to the accident could reach four billion USD, according to analysts quoted by Reuters (Reuters 2024).

Figure 1.1: Wreckage of the Francis Scott Key Bridge in Baltimore after contact with the Dali container ship. Image courtesy US National Transportation Safety Board, public domain. Image source: NTSB website.

At the time of publishing this paper, the investigation into this accident is still ongoing. However, there is agreement among experts that the Francis Scott Key Bridge, designed in the early 1970s, was insufficiently protected from collisions by vessels. The bridge did have some limited protection mechanisms, including “dolphins” and a pier fendering system, as shown in figure 1.2, but these were insufficient to protect the bridge from the impact of a huge cargo vessel such as MS Dali¹.

Figure 1.2: Protection mechanisms on the Francis Scott Key Bridge. Image courtesy US National Transportation Safety Board, public domain. Source: NTSB marine investigation preliminary report DCA24MM031.

Cargo companies have been operating increasingly large container vessels since the 1990s. The Dali container vessel was over 300m in length, and several times heavier than what the Francis Scott Key Bridge had been designed to resist. The risk from a collision was known to experts, and had indeed been demonstrated by the collapse of the Sunshine Skyway Bridge in Florida in 1980, after a vessel struck one of the piers, leading to 35 fatalities and triggering improvements to bridge design codes and to bridge protection mechanisms. The Baltimore Harbor Safety and Coordination Committee, which included representatives of different stakeholders concerned by port infrastructure, such as the owner of the Francis Scott Key Bridge and different bodies with regulatory roles concerning bridge

¹ For an engineering analysis of how safety risks are assessed for bridge protection, see for example a video by Practical Engineering.

design and the operation of marine infrastructure, was aware that larger ships posed a threat to the Francis Scott Key Bridge, and had prepared a plan to improve its protection mechanisms². However, such an upgrade would have been expensive.

Over the same period as the pier protection upgrade was being discussed, the committee was involved in plans to prevent terrorist activities in the harbour area, with funding provided by FEMA. The proposed upgrade to the bridge protection systems was removed from the committee's work plan in 2014, according to minutes examined by the Washington Post.

Our discussion in this paper is mostly focused on bridge protection mechanisms, even if other questions such as the reasons for loss of control of the Dali ship itself are also interesting to analyse. We will discuss the factors that seem to have contributed to the absence of a decision to improve bridge protection, despite clear knowledge of the risks. This case is used to illustrate the critical gaps that often exist in the link between knowledge and decision-making:

- Failure to adapt infrastructure to modern risks: The bridge, designed in the 1970s, was ill-equipped to handle collisions with large, modern container ships like the Dali. Despite knowledge of increasing ship sizes, no significant updates were made to the bridge's protection systems, reflecting a failure to integrate evolving maritime knowledge into risk mitigation strategies.
- Inadequate focus on scenarios of realistic threats: Authorities focused more on the risk of terrorist attacks than on the very real threat posed by modern maritime traffic. Knowledge of past incidents, such as smaller ship collisions, and the growing size of container vessels should have prompted action to reinforce the bridge. However, decision-makers failed to prioritise these risks, contributing to the collapse.
- Outdated protection systems: The bridge's fender system, designed to protect against smaller vessels, was inadequate for vessels of the size of MS Dali. Although newer bridges were required to have stronger protection measures, the Francis Scott Key Bridge was exempt from these regulations due to its age. This is a clear example of how outdated knowledge and regulatory exemptions can lead to infrastructure vulnerabilities.

² A Washington Post article titled *Long before the collapse, safety panel warned of 'ship strikes'* [Thompson and Duncan 2024] includes extracts from minutes of the meetings of the Baltimore Harbor Safety and Coordination Commission dating back to 2004, which show that the collision risk was discussed repeatedly during committee meetings.

- Neglect of early warning signs: Prior to the Dali's collision, there were warnings — such as power outages and technical alarms — that suggested the ship had mechanical issues. However, these signals were not properly escalated or acted upon, showing a gap in operational risk management and decision-making.
- Lack of action on known structural vulnerabilities: The continuous truss design of the bridge, which is fracture-critical, was a known weakness. Despite inspections in 2021 and 2023 finding the bridge in "satisfactory" condition, no decisions were made to address this inherent vulnerability, which ultimately contributed to the rapid failure of the bridge when one support was compromised.

We refer to the continued existence of such gaps between knowledge (please see chapter 4 for a brief discussion of the distinction between knowledge, information and data) and action as a form of organisational blindness. The remainder of this document discusses different reasons for organisational blindness, and measures that can be taken to reduce it.

1.3 Organisational blindness to knowledge

We propose the following definition³ for organisational blindness to knowledge concerning safety issues:

“ *the partial omission of known hazards, scenarios or safety measures from an organisation's design work or operations.* ”

This situation is illustrated in the Francis Scott Key Bridge case, where the absence of work to improve the bridge's collision protection systems, despite clear knowledge of the nature of the safety hazard, highlights the issue.

³ This definition is inspired by the analysis of "assumed risk" developed by the MORT programme, which developed material to support the U.S. nuclear industry's management of safety, health and environmental protection between 1968 and 2002. The notion of assumed risk is summarised at the foot of page 56 in the MORT Users' Manual.

While blindness (to knowledge) can be an individual phenomenon, we focus in this document on blindness at an **organisational level** and as an **organised outcome**. This is similar to the analogies made between individual learning and organisational learning by researchers in behavioural psychology [Argyris and Schön 1978] and management studies [Cyert and March 1963].

As illustrated in the “family tree” of types of blindness to knowledge in figure 1.3, organisational blindness to knowledge may be **unintended**, for example due to:

- blind spots: gaps in knowledge of specific hazards or the availability of effective risk prevention measures;
- information asymmetry: knowledge may be present in one part of the organisation (such as the front-line workers who have day-to-day familiarity with parts of the sociotechnical system and may be aware of anomalies) without it having percolated to the parts of the organisation able to allocate organisational resources to reducing the risk;
- cultural amnesia: investigations into major technological accidents often find that precursors to the accident had arisen and been analysed before, but were progressively forgotten over years of operation without an accident;
- systemic dysfunction: the organisation studies literature contains a wealth of descriptions of issues in organisational structure and behaviour which hinder rational decision-making and resource allocation.

Alternatively, the blindness of an organisation may also be **wilful**, becoming a form of “organised blindness”, for different reasons which are discussed in chapter 3.

In the remainder of this document, we analyse in chapter 2 the impact of organisational complexity, which can lead to blindness which is either unintended or wilful. Chapter 3 analyses the phenomenon of wilful or purposeful blindness. Chapter 4 proposes a number of measures that an organisation can use to help it detect that it may be blind to certain safety issues, with a particular emphasis on the search for early warning signs of safety risks. Chapter 5 proposes strategies that a motivated individual can use to help overcome organisational blindness and ensure that safety issues obtain the attention and resources necessary for good management.

Figure 1.3: The “family tree” of blindness to knowledge. Figure developed by the ESReDA project group on Risk, Knowledge and Management.

A common thread to these different sections is a question often discussed during meetings of the ESReDA project group on risk, knowledge and management: What do you need to know to manage safety and make appropriate decisions?

Organisational complexity as a source of blindness

Authors: Eric Marsden and Ana Lisa Vetere Arellano

2.1 The concept and the claim

We argue in this chapter that organisational complexity and the diffusion of responsibility for safety makes accidents almost inevitable in the long term.

We use the term organisational complexity to describe situations where managing and governing a sociotechnical system depends on the collaboration and coordination of many different organisations, such as firms, agencies, government bodies, and stakeholder groups. In these cases, responsibility for the system's performance, including its safety, is shared across multiple organisations and individuals. However, the people who have the expertise to spot hazards and suggest ways to deal with risks often do not have the authority or resources to act on them. As a result, individuals may hesitate to make high-stakes decisions or may avoid addressing certain problems, assuming that others involved will handle them instead.

2.1.1 The concept of practical drift

Over time, sociotechnical systems can evolve in directions that often lead to increased safety risks. This phenomenon is called “practical drift” or “drift to danger” in the organisation studies literature [Rasmussen 1997; Snook 2000]. It occurs when people optimise the system's functioning at the micro level, without periodically rethinking the checks and balances that were set up at the time the system was designed.

For example, in the case of the Francis Scott Key Bridge, the trend towards increasingly large cargo vessels rendered the bridge protection mechanisms inadequate. Unless countered by actions to control the risks (such as an investment in the upgrade of the bridge protection mechanisms), the system will continue drifting towards unsafe operation, and eventually towards an accident.

2.1.2 Active inertia and organisational response

The phenomenon of active inertia, an organisation's tendency to follow established patterns of behaviour even when the environment changes¹, means that organisations have a limited ability to spontaneously decide that disruptive safety upgrades are needed. This means that the drift to danger is rarely interrupted unless an active regulator requires changes.

2.2 Facts and interpretation of cases

Figure 2.1 illustrates the different organisations (US government agencies, state government departments, associations and committees, stakeholder groups) that were involved in the regulation and the operations of the Francis Scott Key Bridge in Baltimore. In particular, the Maryland Transit Administration, a component of the Maryland Department of Transportation, was the owner of the bridge. The Federal Highway Administration publishes technical advisory documents on issues such as pier protection for bridges, and the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials publishes guidance documents on the retrofit of collision protection mechanisms for existing road infrastructure. The US Coast Guard sometimes provides funding for modifications to transport infrastructure that interferes with navigation, but cannot mandate such modifications itself. Likewise, the US Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) can provide funding for modifications to critical infrastructure, sometimes including bridges. The Baltimore Harbor Safety and Coordination Committee brought together experts from these different organisations, and was specifically focused on safety issues, but did not have a mandate or a budget to require changes.

This situation of multiple organisations involved in regulation and management is not uncommon for complex infrastructure such as large industrial ports, where maritime traffic crosses road traffic and the number of stakeholders is significant. It was also present in several well-known disasters: for example, the following figure illustrates the relationships between the parties involved in the Grenfell Tower highrise fire (London, 2017) where inappropriate building materials were used for the cladding of a block of flats, leading to the death of 17 people.

¹ The concept of active inertia is due to management scholar Donald Sull, who points to a number of cases of successful industrial firms that failed to meet the challenge of necessary change [Sull 2009]. Examples include Polaroid, who failed to recognise the rising threat to its business selling photographic film from digital cameras, and the Firestone tire maker which failed to react to the innovation represented by radial tires.

Figure 2.1: The stakeholders involved in the management and the oversight of safety issues on the Francis Scott Key Bridge. Original work by the authors.

Figure 2.2: The “web of blame” in which were intertwined the parties in the inquiry into the Grenfell Tower disaster. Nineteen organisations and 58 individuals were concerned by the investigation. This figure reproduced from material presented by the counsel to the Grenfell Tower Inquiry, Richard Millett KC. This figure is excluded from our CC BY license.

A similar situation of organisational complexity was seen in the Deepwater Horizon disaster (USA, 2010), where multiple companies were involved in defining the conditions that led to the accident (the operator of the drilling operation, BP, the owner of the rig, Transocean, the company responsible for the cementing operation, Halliburton, the manufacturer of the “blowout prevention” safety equipment used in the well, and multiple contractor firms with employees present on the rig). There were 17 “parties in interest” at the trial.

Organisational complexity means that work processes often require collaboration and coordination across organisational boundaries. This leads to:

- different sets of rules for same activity
- obstacles to flow of information
- unclear accountability structures

In these types of situations, we see a phenomenon of diffusion of responsibility: people feel less responsibility for taking action in a given situation, because there are other people who could also be responsible (and held accountable) for taking action. This leads to accountability mismatches. In the Francis Scott Key Bridge case, a member of the Baltimore Harbor Safety and Coordination Committee quoted by the Washington Post [Thompson and Duncan 2024] (article titled *Long before the collapse, safety panel warned of ‘ship strikes’* dated May 24th 2024) stated:

“It’s obvious that the lines of authority are not clear, or not well understood... It looks like everybody’s passing the buck.”

In the Grenfell Tower case, the counsel to the inquiry into the accident noted that companies and government bodies were “indulging in a merry-go-round of blame”. The report of the public inquiry notes [Moore-Bick et al. 2024, p. 18] that

“Everyone involved in the choice of the materials to be used in the external wall thought that responsibility for their suitability and safety lay with someone else.”

In the Deepwater Horizon case, some efforts at blame shifting were seen in the aftermath of the accident, such as BP titling its first news statement after the accident “Gulf of Mexico – Transocean Drilling Incident” [Soraghan 2010], and its CEO stating

“This wasn’t our accident. This was a drilling rig operated by another company. It was their people, their systems, their processes.”²

² Source: Interview with NBC’s Today show. <https://www.bbc.com/news/10360084>

Increasing the number of individuals and roles that can be seen as holding responsibility for safety, weakens, rather than strengthens, the associated accountability for the duty of ensuring safe operation. This “social shirking” effect is the opposite of the “defence in depth” principle which underlies many other safety management practices.

Responsible decision-making concerning safety requires the following³:

- Acceptance of a duty to prevent harm by some organisation or organisations, the duty holder;
- Accountability for the duty;
- Capability to fulfil the duty, which requires the duty holder to (1) have the authority and resources needed to implement changes, (2) to have access to data and information concerning risks, and institutional memory of the incidents and operating conditions that can threaten safety, and (3) to possess the competency to understand threats and decide on prevention measures.

These features are weakened in the presence of organisational complexity. Indeed, the acceptance of a duty and the accountability for that duty are both weakened by diffusion of responsibility. The authority and resources that are needed to implement changes tend to be spread across multiple organisations, and coordination issues will make it difficult to make decisions. Information and knowledge concerning hazards can fall into the “cracks” between organisations. When these features are not present, an accident becomes much more likely, as the three cases discussed above illustrate.

These problems affect both the companies involved in operating a system or critical infrastructure, and the regulatory and inspection bodies responsible for safety governance and safety oversight.

Organisational complexity is often generated over time, emerging organically as a result of successive small changes each aiming to associate a new stakeholder in the management and governance of the system. In other cases, the organisational complexity may be produced deliberately, as a way of avoiding accountability, either by limiting the ability of decision-makers to act on knowledge of safety risks, or by avoiding the knowledge ever reaching them.

³ After [Shaw and Barry 1989].

For these reasons, we argue that organisational complexity is an **institutional anti-pattern** (an undesirable feature of the organisational structure) for high-hazard systems and infrastructures. Oversight bodies should have the ability to recognise this anti-pattern, and the power to mandate structural changes that increase the clarity of accountability for safety.

2.3 Results of the interactive session: claims, examples and questions

During the 65th ESREDA Seminar in Athens, participants discussed the challenges in managing organisational complexity and the diffusion of responsibility in large infrastructure systems, using the Francis Scott Key Bridge accident in Baltimore as an example. A lack of centralised oversight and the diffusion of responsibility among numerous stakeholders led to ineffective action, highlighting the need for clearer structures and accountability.

The outcome of the discussion can be grouped into four main issues, portrayed below.

2.3.1 Challenges in complex organisational structures

In complex organisational structures with multiple stakeholders, several challenges arise that hinder effective response and decision-making. These include:

- Lack of clear accountability, leading to a “pass the buck” mindset;
- Poor maintenance and limited funding due to insufficient regulatory clarity;
- Blame shifting between stakeholders in the event of disasters like wildfires and floods;
- Limited transparency and intentional avoidance of safety information, hindering decision-makers’ ability to act on risks based on knowledge acquired;
- Interconnected systems can increase risk due to potential miscommunication or conflicting decisions among multiple stakeholders.

2.3.2 Designing accountable systems

To build systems with clear responsibility and accountability, the following strategies can be employed:

- Managing increasing complexity with subcontractors;
- Establishing “stop rules” to improve accountability and communication;
- Defining explicit criteria for decision-making on issues like outsourcing or delegating work.

2.3.3 Effective management of high-risk situations

To manage high-risk situations effectively, the following principles can be applied:

- Appointing a leading organisation to make final decisions and allocate resources;
- Establishing clear roles, authority paths, and accountability metrics for each stakeholder;
- Fostering effective communication and collaboration to overcome siloed operations and differing stakeholder values.

2.3.4 Mitigating risks through regulation and competency building

To mitigate the risks associated with organisational complexity, the following approaches can be taken:

- Implementing strong regulatory frameworks to fill gaps in decision-making and safety enforcement;
- Avoiding over-reliance on outsourcing by balancing it with internal competency building;
- Maintaining institutional knowledge and reducing risk through rotational roles;
- Holding external partners to account (both in the sense of collaborative and relational accountability, asking partners to share their accounts of what might go wrong and what is important, and in the more standard negative sense of being held accountable).

2.4 Conclusions with respect to safety risks

The discussion during the seminar and within the project group points to a number of “organisational anti-patterns” related to organisational complexity and fragmentation of accountability for safety, that can be recognised in a range of high-hazard systems and critical infrastructures. These lead to lack of accountability for decisions related to safety, unclear regulatory scopes, lack of ownership of the associated responsibilities. They make it less likely that decisions which would be necessary to ensure safety in an evolving context, but which involve costs for some stakeholders, will indeed be made. They allow the system to “drift” towards an accident, which becomes almost inevitable over long timeframes. These organisational anti-patterns tend to be more present for “neglected”⁴ infrastructure, which is characterised by limited funding available to ensure adequate maintenance and safe operation over long timeframes.

We acknowledge that the complex multi-stakeholder organisational forms that we criticise are not created with malicious intent. They result from a desire to implement the democratic principles of participatory governance, which holds that organisations and individuals that hold a stake in the effective operation of the system or infrastructure (“stakeholders”) sometimes are the best informed regarding risks and benefits of possible decisions, and should have a say in consequential decisions. It is a challenge to allow participation without weakening accountability for safety and effective risk management.

The framework that regulates how stakeholders engage and collaborate is of importance to help organisations “do governance” and gain foresight, in particular concerning safety risks.

Another point of caution is that monolithic operating organisations are not a magical solution to the problems highlighted in this section, because many large organisations also suffer from internal conflicts (between divisions, professional groups, organisational leaders) which in some sense echo those seen in the complex organisational structures that we have described.

⁴ The term “neglected infrastructure” is somewhat controversial depending on the meaning given to the term “neglect”. Synonyms for neglect include negligence (which can be criminal), oversights, blindness, and missed opportunities. Some of these are much more accusatory than others.

Being wilfully blind

Authors: John Kingston and Sever Paul

How we think about blindness to knowledge varies with the level of awareness or agency involved.

At one extreme, certain types of information tend not to reach the decision makers of the organisation. Rather than random loss, there is a pattern, but not one that the makers of the decisions affected might be aware of. The pattern may be due to dominant ways of thinking – paradigms or mindsets – that value certain types of knowledge over others, and which leave out some types entirely.

At the other extreme is the knowing omission of critical facts from a decision. An agent to the decision knew that such facts might exist, but, to avoid constraining the decision, contrived or allowed a situation that left those facts out.

Between those extremes is a broad middle ground. Closer to the “wilful” end are decisions affected by subconscious psychological mechanisms, such as Festinger’s cognitive dissonance [Festinger 1957] or Argyris’s skilled-unawareness [Argyris 1994] and skilled-incompetence. Towards the other extreme, are organisations set up in ways to avoid accountability; ways that either remove agency from decision makers to act on knowledge, or which avoid the knowledge ever being placed in their hands.

Cognitive dissonance and skilled unawareness

Each of us, it can be argued, has a mental model of the world and ourselves. The model guides our plans and informs how we interpret new facts. This model is largely implicit, wordless, and not fully available to introspection. In these respects, it is quite different from the explicit, external and testable theories of science.

The term *cognitive dissonance* describes the discomfort sometimes felt when new facts do not fit with our mental model. It assumes a basic role for emotion in regulating how we think and what we do. This is emotion in its most primitive sense: subjective feelings of pleasure, comfort or discomfort. If uncomfortable, we change what we can until we are comfortable again.

The literature of cognitive dissonance seeks to predict and explain how people alter their thinking or actions to avoid discomfort. People, it seems, are quite conservative – their mental model is part of their identity. Changing the model means changing the self. Therefore, when uncomfortable, we prefer to change the facts by altering our perceptions or by operating, if we can, on the source of the facts.

Perception is a creative process, not a faithful mapping of data into our mental model. Filtering and weighing data occur below the threshold of awareness – mostly. We are aware of the results but not the process, or of our biases. Reflecting on these results is something that we can do, certainly, but it requires opportunity and an effort of will.

An important point is that one’s own behaviour forms part of the data, and so is subject to the same creative processes of perception. Chris Argyris points out that we do not see the effects of our actions on others or spot our biases in operation [Argyris 1994]. Furthermore, he suggests that this unawareness is a skill – something we can improve both in effectiveness and speed. He concludes,

“ Asked to examine their own behaviour or the behaviour of subordinates, people in this situation are likely:

- To reason defensively and to interact with others who are reasoning defensively;
- To get superficial, single-loop responses that lead to superficial, single-loop solutions;
- To reinforce the organisational defensive routines that inhibit access to valid information and genuine learning;

- *To be unaware of their own defences because these are so skilled and automatic; and,*
- *To be unaware that they are producing any of these consequences, or, if they are aware of defensiveness, to see it only in others.*

Blindness to knowledge is hard to study, and what we know about it is tentative and contentious. What constitutes critical information is often only really clear in retrospect — when the accident has happened or the court case has begun. Also, aside from egregious cases of wrongdoing (e.g. persecuting whistleblowers, shredding incriminating records), most blindness to knowledge is suspected rather than proved, or hidden even from the decision-maker's self-awareness. However, not knowing the molecular basis of genes did not stop Mendel doing useful work on plant breeding; we can theorise from surface phenomena and so make useful predictions. Awareness of types of blindness and their possible mechanisms gives options to detecting it and improving safety management.

3.1 The concept and the claim

Wilful blindness is the deliberate or subconscious omission of relevant knowledge from a decision. Omission can be absolute: the absence of a known fact from a decision. But it can also be partial, such as the distortion of a fact or of its weight in a decision.

The claim made in the poster session was that wilful blindness stops needed engineering upgrades. In other words, there are occasions when decision makers remove, avoid, or distort key data that would otherwise commit their organisation to making a costly, inconvenient change. This claim was made to stimulate debate about how knowledge “flows” in decision-making. The aim was to remind people working in this area that the challenges to improved decision-making are not purely technocratic, but social also.

What makes wilful blindness more likely? The Athens seminar poster presented a list of behaviours and conditions that drive and sustain wilful blindness. No scientific claim is made here in the sense of demonstrated cause and effect. The aim was to communicate the concept and to stimulate discussion. The items on the list can be grouped into behaviours and conditions.

- Defensive behaviours — usually, those of leaders, in specific response to facts that threaten their positions, their good opinion of themselves or, in

Dalton's memorable phrase [Dalton 1959], threaten the “dignity of the organisation”.

- Punish or ignore whistleblowers;
- Suppress dissent or criticism;
- Create fear of repercussions.
- Concealing behaviours — that distort facts or reduce their weight in decisions, or which inhibit communication of facts to people with power.
 - Downplay negative information;
 - Create ambiguity (plausible deniability);
 - Avoid conflict;
 - Avoid transparency.
- Corrupting behaviours — that move workers' norms away from valuing safety and taking personal responsibility for it.
 - Emphasise loyalty and conformity;
 - Reward silence, support the status quo;
 - Normalise ethical lapses and small acts of misconduct;
 - Leaders visibly ignore problems.
- Corrupting conditions — norms and baseline knowledge within an organisation that enable the above behaviours and which those behaviours reinforce. These conditions include:
 - Poor awareness of risk;
 - Weak accountability for safety issues;
 - Groupthink and herd mentality;
 - Belief in success at any cost;
 - Prioritisation of short-term gains over long-term risks.

3.2 Facts and interpretation of cases

Since its opening in 1977, the Francis Scott Key Bridge disaster was foreseen and discussed. Although it is not known whether any engineered protection could have enabled the bridge to withstand a collision with the Dali, it is clear that the risk existed and stakeholders were on record saying that the risk needed reduction [Thompson and Duncan 2024]. The knowledge of the risk was available to decision-makers, yet no decision about how to treat the risk appears to have been made.

The Francis Scott Key Bridge disaster appears to be a case study in blindness to knowledge. What is not clear now, but might become clear after investigation, is whether the management teams responsible for the bridge and the port ever operated with foresight of the risk. And, if they did, how did they — and indeed the wider system of governance in which they were embedded — become blind to the knowledge that the bridge would not withstand a collision with the heavier vessels in that waterway?

Might the concept of blindness to knowledge be useful to get purchase on a very slippery question: how would we know before an accident if a management team is responsible? One of the causes of the slipperiness is the word “responsibility”, which can be used in several ways. Responsibility, as mentioned in chapter 2, can be seen as having three senses [Shaw and Barry 1989]:

- to have a duty (to be responsible for something);
- to be accountable (to be supported in a duty to look after something, judged for its fulfilment, and rewarded or punished for conduct);
- to be capable (of acting responsibly).

We can apply “blindness to knowledge” in each of these three:

- blindness to a duty, or some aspect of it;
- blindness to accountability;
- blindness to facts and causal relationships.

One can imagine the three senses of responsibility as lines that weave individuals and their organisations into a network that turns energy into goods. These lines will be manifest as contract clauses, regulations, job descriptions, method statements, verbal agreements, indeed all the ways in which expectations are expressed. Imagine then the effects of blindness in the lines and knots of that network: holes through which energies escape containment and do harm. Arguably, the Deepwater Horizon is an example, but unfortunately there are many others.

The Francis Scott Key Bridge accident stimulated the authors’ thinking about blindness to knowledge, and gave them a case to stimulate discussion at the seminar. If the details are ever established, it may be a valuable case study in how normal people working in reputable organisations can be blind to known, unaccepted risks.

3.2.1 Wilful Blindness and its contribution to accidents

Some accidents happen even in situations in which risks are foreseen and well-managed. Usually, some risk remains even when precautions are taken. However, many accidents reflect limitations in the assessment or management of risks. These limitations might be technical in nature, but might sometimes reflect wilful blindness by decision makers with a duty to foresee risk or put precautions in place. To put it another way, the approaches and routines for managing risks can be subverted to avoid certain facts or conclusions. Risk assessment and other methods are not proof against wilful blindness, and although some methods are harder to subvert than others, none are immune.

One comes across this subversion from time to time: a manager who adopts a “respected” method to create an aura of authority for conclusions reached by abusing the method. A con-trick in short. When the NRI foundation revised Events and Conditional Factors Analysis [NRI 2014], it took on board Ludwig Benner’s observations of how his original version of the method was open to abuse. NRI tightened up the ECFA rule set, but like whack-a-mole, this does not stop user-bias and force-fitting from moving elsewhere in the investigative process.

Risk assessment is a formal process that organises how people act on a risk, but there are informal processes too. Of the latter type, positional power is particularly relevant. Directly or indirectly, people with more power can silence those who have less. Ironically, those with less power are often closer to the interface with hazards and have greater subject matter knowledge about the associated risks and precautions. The silence can create managerial freedom to allocate resources to things that are productive, albeit with more risk. Furthermore, as [Morrison and Milliken 2000] point out, “organisational silence” not only preserves the power structure, but also compromises the organisation’s ability to detect and correct error. If the probabilities of the system allow (i.e. low frequency, low severity accident potentials), a manager may never have to face the consequences of neglecting the facts they have suppressed, the errors they have not corrected. This can establish habits and skills in a manager that they might take with them into higher risk settings, where the probabilities or consequences are less forgiving.

Organisational silence and pressure from people who hold power in the organisation can be used to allocate resources to activities and options that increase production, but which also considerably increase risks.

On the proactive side of risk management, suppressing the upward flow of information can also push risk acceptance downward in an uncontrolled way. This makes accidents more likely because risks are accepted at too low a level in the organisation and without the reviews and technical support needed to make an informed decision about a risk.

Robert Jackall describes one way this can happen [Jackall 1988, p. 22]:

“ ... Pushing down details relieves superiors of the burden of too much knowledge, particularly guilty knowledge. A superior will say to a subordinate, for instance: “Give me your best thinking on the problem with [X].” When the subordinate makes his report [i.e. the solution to X, but without all of its details], he is often told: “I think you can do better than that”, until the subordinate has worked out all the details of the boss’s predetermined solution, without the boss being specifically aware of “all the eggs that have to be broken”.

This stops the upward flow of knowledge about risks, especially those risks that should only be accepted at higher levels of the organisation. In this way, organisations can create risks without managerial oversight, risks that might not be accepted had a risk assessment process been operating properly (i.e. as envisaged in ISO 31000:2018).

On the reactive side of risk management, suppressing the upward flow of inconvenient facts also means that weak signals are suppressed. Hence, changes are not adapted to in a timely way, leaving the associated risks unmanaged.

The McNamara fallacy offers another insight into the “mechanisms” of blindness. In the narrow sense, the fallacy describes how blindness to risks can result from overreliance on numerical methods. Blindness occurs when a measurement is wrongly interpreted to mean “safe” or when qualitative evidence of a problem is disregarded because it is not numerical. More generally, however, the fallacy describes how managers can ‘misinform their internal representation of the systems they control and, by extension, misinform their foresight of those systems when planning or evaluating change’ [Kingston and Dien 2020, p 14].

3.2.2 This is how to recognise wilful blindness

Organised blindness is present when facts that should be in play, are not there. Independent auditors, inspectors and investigators — that is, people external to the organisation — are likely to be familiar with this situation. It is much harder for people within the organisation to spot facts that are concealed by wilful blindness. If they do see the facts but lack power, they will either succumb to kinds of strategies listed above (§ 3.1) or contrive their own blindness (e.g. via cognitive dissonance, or skilled unawareness).

It is likely that employees will see every day the behaviours that produce wilful blindness. The problem for safety is that these behaviours are normal, meaning socially acceptable to others in the workplace. Hence, in the benign setting, the behaviours are useful; only in the risky setting are they a problem. Usually, it’s only in retrospect that we can tell the benign from the risky. In real-time, in contrast, we might not recognise the mismatch because part of the behaviour, as [Argyris 1994] notes, is unawareness of the behaviour.

Many of the behaviours that produce wilful blindness are socially acceptable and even useful in organisations without major accident hazards. They become problematic when they lead to critical safety-related facts being “swept under the carpet”, allowing the system to continue drifting towards an accident.

As mentioned, many of the behaviours that produce wilful blindness are socially acceptable and useful in a benign setting. The description given by [Argyris 1988] of a Model I strategy looks rather monstrous, but might not be seen that way by subordinates. [Jackall 1988], shows how “dexterity with symbols” enables managers to enact Model I with charm and tact. The problem is when this setting is risky and critical facts are hidden beneath the gloss.

Model I strategy (after [Argyris 1988])

- Define goals and try to achieve them unilaterally. The manager focuses on winning and being “right” rather than engaging in open dialogue.
- Maximise control. The manager tries to control the conversation or decision-making process to minimise their own vulnerability.
- Suppress negative emotions. The manager avoids addressing discomfort and doubts, and dismisses challenges.
- Act defensively and blame others. If something has gone wrong, the manager blames those involved and does not engage in self-reflection.

It can be argued that wilful blindness will propagate across and down through organisational hierarchies. Imagine a “case zero” of wilful blindness: a manager who wants to do “x”. The manager suspects that reasons for not doing “x” could be found if looked for. The manager contrives to be blind to these suspicions (e.g. cognitive bias — look only for evidence that supports doing “x”, and avoid or disregard evidence that goes against doing “x”). The manager is now wilfully blind to this whole class of facts. But others are not; they can see those problematic facts. If those “sighted” people have the same goals as the blinded, or have less power but depend on the manager, they will be motivated to blind themselves. If they challenge, the manager can silence them (or blind them) using the strategies already mentioned.

3.2.3 The causes of wilful blindness

When decision-makers turn a blind eye to risks or a deaf ear to demands to act, we despair of the resulting accidents. It is tempting to see causation as the Courts must: within a logic of culpability. There is undoubtedly room for more effective regulation and innovative ways to apply it. This, however, applies at the organisational structure end of the blindness spectrum.

At the individual and small-group end of the spectrum, the causes of wilful blindness are interwoven with daily life. Many of the authors who have written on this subject acknowledge that wilful blindness is produced by behaviours that are normal [Heffernan 2011; Lessig 2011; Argyris 1999; Jackall 1988; Nader 2016; Luban 1999]. David Luban captures the essence [Luban 1999]:

“Deniability is the key to succeeding at the world’s work, which is often dirty, while keeping a clean conscience — or at least a serviceable facsimile of a clean conscience. Evading truth is an expedient for avoiding lies. It’s a stratagem for tarnished angels like you and me, not for unrepentant scoundrels. It’s the homage that vice pays to virtue.

The point is that the behaviours that produce wilful blindness are normal and often useful. However, the same behaviours that deliver goods can also deliver accidents and harm. Might it be possible to recognise the circumstances in which these normal behaviours are, in fact, too risky? And, if it is possible, might it also be possible to have a usable set of alternative behaviours that are safer?

3.2.4 Avoiding and challenging wilful blindness

What might be done to manage the individual and small-group behaviours that produce wilful blindness in decision-makers? Organised blindness, this paper has argued, can be considered as a spectrum. At one end the focus is on individuals and small groups, their decisions and their behaviours. At the other end are organisational structures and the design of them to create screens between laws and corporate behaviour — discussion about options to manage these can be found in chapter 2.

Developing prescriptions to avoid wilful blindness needs more knowledge about the behaviours and conditions that produce it. Investigations after accidents and scandals have produced lots of findings, but these are scattered. This knowledge needs to be systematised to better typify the behaviours of interest and the conditions under which they create safety problems. Perhaps this might be susceptible to the data scraping capabilities of research using artificial intelligence.

An obstacle to research and practice is the sensitivity of the topic in the workplace. As indicated, below, wilful blindness tends to be entangled with issues of culpability. As a result, discussion tends to be freighted with discomfiting and controversial assumptions. Wilful blindness is something of a taboo subject, and this “undiscussability” inhibits addressing the problem. Even a list that describes the behaviours and conditions of interest might serve to legitimise discussion of wilful blindness.

As well as scraping past cases, there is a role for gathering primary data — of “solutions” as well as “problems”. Given the subtlety and subjectivity of the phenomena, presumably research will need to be variations of sociological approaches such as participant action research (PAR), and anthropological approaches like participant observation. Concerning the latter, Melville Dalton’s

Men Who Manage remains an instructive example [Dalton 1959]. However, requiring as it does, considerable time and resources, this research would need commitment.

Although the evidence base is weak, it is still possible to identify some principles for research and action. First, we should recognise that the behaviours that produce wilful blindness are not, for the most part, intrinsically immoral or corrupt. In most instances, the behaviour is prosocial rather than the opposite – tactfulness and politeness, for example. The behaviours that produce wilful blindness are a problem when they are exhibited in a system with large accident potentials. The problem then is not the behaviour *per se*, but the misfit between the behaviour and the context. We need both to recognise this misfit and have other models, other standards, that guide how we inform a decision when the risks demand it.

Being ethical or being rude? How politeness enables organised blindness

In many national cultures, respect for colleagues is associated with communicating with tact and politeness, and avoiding raising issues that might be embarrassing. When discussing safety concerns, this can lead to incomprehension (“surely she understood my hint”) or to avoidance of discussions and decisions that should be made. Problems can be “swept under the carpet”, remaining hidden in gaps between the organisational responsibility of individuals or below the threshold of concern that would normally trigger action. Organisations cannot act on every concern (indeed, Diane Vaughan noted that organisations are defined as much by what they choose to overlook as by what they pay attention to¹), so these problems can remain unresolved for long periods of time. While this organisational and human characteristic is not uncommon, it becomes ethically problematic when the organisation is responsible for managing major accident hazards or can lead to significant harm to society.

People need to be able to “speak truth to power”, to show what defensive colleagues might call a level of “paranoia” concerning risks, to irritate their coworkers by pushing back on “it will be fine” and “we’ll address that in next year’s action plan” responses to their concerns.

[Hayes et al. 2021] list the ability of engineers to “advocate for action and take responsibility” as one of the core non-technical skills that a “capable engineer” should possess. In a related paper [Maslen et al. 2021], the authors mention that “muteness on ethical matters can obscure the nature of the risk where technical advice is being taken on by non-technical ac-

tors, and where technical actors themselves do not have a clear sense of their public safety obligations”. We would add that these should be core skills of a manager or leader of such organisations, though these competencies are distributed less homogeneously than they would be in the best of worlds.

Ideally, a third way between being rude and being blind can be found, based on courtesy and respect for the value of questioning accepted practices and specific decisions. As an example, asking a medical doctor for a second opinion concerning certain high-consequence decisions should be seen as a routine matter, rather than as a declaration of distrust or disrespect.

The behaviours that produce wilful blindness are not, in general, intrinsically immoral; many are social conveniences such as politeness and tactfulness. However, in high-risk environments where accidents can have severe consequences, these behaviours can be detrimental. In such situations, it’s crucial to be able to challenge authority, be vigilant, and question assumptions, even if it means being perceived as overly cautious or annoying to others. Simply accepting “it will be fine” as an answer is not enough; instead, we need to be willing to speak up and express concerns to ensure safety.

Model I behaviour is an example of actions that are useful in the right setting, but risky for safety. [Argyris and Schön 1978] make clear that Model I behaviours are habitual and ubiquitous. When exhibited by a leader, the behaviour discourages collaborative problem-solving, inquiry and learning. In a benign situation, this might be a price worth paying for speed, avoiding embarrassment, and reinforcing confidence in the status quo. In a risky environment, however, it preserves the leader’s blindness of certain facts, and perhaps blinds others; especially when the behaviour is habitual.

Model I illustrates another principle: like many of the behaviours that produce wilful blindness, unawareness of the behaviour is part of the behaviour – the leader does not know that they are doing it. Argyris reports that, even when the leader is made aware of their Model I behaviours and its downsides, they

¹ Diane Vaughan’s report into the Challenger space shuttle disaster noted that NASA’s organisational culture “provided a way of seeing that was simultaneously a way of not seeing” [Vaughan 1996].

continue to exhibit the behaviour when similar situations arise in the future. Model I is very hard to extinguish by training. Perhaps teachable metacognitive, reflective techniques can be found — this also is a research need.

Wilful blindness has psychological and social aspects; both offer ways into the problem. Although reflective techniques might help individual practitioners gain internal control of their wilful blindness, research should review the value of external, team-led approaches. In that respect, there is probably a lot of mileage in what we already know about how to manage risks and manage projects. Project review gates, supervisory planned observations, independent reviews of risk studies, incident investigations, critical incident studies, operational readiness practices, etc., all aim to make visible the risks and inefficiencies that undetected undermine safety. However, the author's own practice suggests that all such approaches gradually become aligned with the avoidance of inconvenient facts — they get corrupted, as it were, with a small 'c'. These approaches need constant renewal to stop them becoming incurious and performative; perhaps wider recognition of wilful blindness would help motivate management to do this.

Lastly, a low base of risk awareness is a factor in wilful blindness. Knowledge about risks needs to be accessible and shared within the organisation. One of the lessons from the US nuclear industry is the importance of technical information systems to managing risks. The criteria laid out in The MORT users' manual [NRI 2009, p. 5–10] are a basis for an information environment that helps make knowledge available and keep it up-to-date. The accent here is on systems; meaning, a growing, vibrant aspect of the workplace in which knowledge grows and in which lifelong learning is integral. Awareness of risks is itself an antidote to some species of wilful blindness. However, awareness suggests a passivity, whereas [Garforth et al. 2018] argue that enabling workers to actively ask questions and find answers is also needed. Increasing the agency of individual workers in finding knowledge may offer another dimension in which to manage wilful blindness.

3.3 Results of the interactive session: claims, examples and questions

Participants agreed that needed upgrades are sometimes stopped by wilful blindness. The discussion also revealed the sensitivity of the topic: we are cautious and watch our words when discussing it. The poster session also underlined the lack of strategies needed to deal with wilful blindness and its precursors.

As one participant noted, the optimism of small business owners can be seen as an exercise in wilful blindness. Entrepreneurs take risks and, when the exposures and energies are small, the worst that happens is the business fails before any serious safety accident occurs. And most start-ups do fail. However, the entrepreneurially useful habits of wilful blindness are dangerous when exhibited by leaders working in settings with large energies and numbers of exposures, as the Dali and Boeing 737 Max cases appear to show.

Even if we could create an organisational blueprint for bastions of rectitude, the VUCA world would make its walls porous. The Boeing case is shocking because the bastion, and its defences of reliable compliance, was overthrown by business risk-takers. Less obvious, yet comparable, is the interfacing of social groups with quite different norms of wilful blindness. Several participants pointed out that the culture of IT is dominated by a culture described variously as “if it works, don't touch it” and “it's good enough”. Hence, even if the requirements by one group are well-informed with respect to risk, the execution of those requirements by a less scrupulous group can undermine them.

Individuals are vulnerable to cognitive bias — we seek information that supports what we believe, and avoid or discount information that contradicts it. Think of the ease with which most of us as well-informed citizens buy IT services and clothes made in the sweatshops of the global south. This weakness was known in antiquity, visible even in Roman law as the maxim “*nemo iudex in causa sua*” — no one should be a judge in their own case. However, the reality is that we every day act as our own judges. The question is how, like Courts acting on the maxim, organisations can be alert to, and act on, judgements that deny or ignore knowledge needed to decide matters of safety.

Our participants also noted that wilful blindness seems to be at work in discussions of reasonable practicability. We are talking about the sweet spot between a set of risk controls that would not reduce the risk enough, and those controls that would be grossly disproportionate to the risk. The theoretical difficulties of ALARP are well known, but wilful blindness provides an interesting perspective on some of the practical difficulties. Participants mentioned various aspects of wilful blindness in ALARP decisions. These included: how experts are selected, how good practice is determined, how standard-setting bodies are governed, and how risks themselves are framed.

Wilful blindness is a dynamic, progressive phenomenon. Sight, as it were, gets worse gradually and is not easily restored. The literature suggests that the conditions for wilful blindness, and specific instances of it, are achieved in a series of steps rather than in one single act of deception. The concept of ethical fading implies a similar incrementalism. A participant noted that this dynamic has a

social inertia that, when finally opposed, is not easy to reverse. In practice, a group that migrates in increments to a new deviant norm is very reluctant to reverse its steps.

As well as distorting both data and sampling, hindsight bias and criminal retribution focus attention on individuals. As ethical fading and diffusion of responsibility show, if we focus solely on individuals we will miss ways to manage wilful blindness. However, if we go too far the other way, to a macro view, we will also miss things. It is useful to recognise a “don’t ask, don’t tell” culture, but it is hard to undo once embedded. Therefore, wilful blindness needs to connect these extremes – the individual and the corporate – with research at the meso-level: the middle ground.

Arguably, managing wilful blindness aligns well with stakeholder engagement. Building relationships means an increase in trust, mutual understanding, quality of communication, and so forth. One would expect a well-engaged workforce to provide a useful defence against wilful blindness. The contrary would also be true, and further complicates the picture with political game-playing. As one of our participants noted, it can be hard for a manager to distinguish between valid concerns and the flexing of an agenda.

Quantity of stakeholder engagement is not the same as quality. Just as industrial relations can be ritualised and inefficient, so can stakeholder relations. As [Brunsson 2002] noted, public services can cultivate what he called, organised hypocrisy – talking in inverse proportion to action. Brunsson was being descriptive rather than judgmental; he points out that endless discussion is a managerial option for containing issues that they see as insoluble. The problem is that organised hypocrisy both locks-in the issue and legitimises a strategy of wilful blindness. Perhaps, the many years spent fruitlessly discussing the collision risk at the Francis Scott Key Bridge Safety Committee is an example of this.

One of the participants spoke of his disappointment to find, on returning to his country after twenty years away, that some problems were unchanged. Furthermore, when one level of government is challenged, there is an adeptness at blaming the level above. At this scale and level, wilful blindness creates its own class of risks, a metarisk as it were, of losing public trust in institutions and the wider political process; adding to VUCA dynamics.

3.4 Conclusions for safety

Wilful blindness is the outcome of a range of psychosocial processes that create degrees of freedom in decisions, at the expense of controlling risks, especially safety risks. Whereas risk management seeks to inform decision-making about safety concerns, wilful blindness is the opposite. Wilful blindness reduces the weight that “safety facts” have in a decision.

Wilful blindness processes lie on a spectrum from deliberate to subconscious. Furthermore, the phenomena of interest are dynamic, affecting systems and cultures that perpetuate weaknesses in how risks are managed. These processes represent opportunities to improve how VUCA risks are managed and regulated.

There is a negative halo around wilful blindness that makes it difficult to study and manage. It is something of a taboo subject. Research into it is usually done in retrospect after an accident has happened or a crime detected. Wilful blindness, as one participant pointed out, is vulnerable to hindsight bias. Therefore, as well as clouded by sampling and data quality problems, wilful blindness processes tend to be viewed through a judgmental lens. This is reinforced in legal practice, which treats wilful blindness as an aspect of culpability – as recklessness and negligence.

Although the end results of wilful blindness processes are sometimes egregious, most of its sub-processes and conditions are mundane. In the list of behaviours and conditions presented earlier, some are reprehensible (e.g. punishing whistleblowers) but most are ordinary features of working life. Indeed, in a benign setting, the behaviours are positive. However, in the context of safety, especially when dealing with large concentrations of energy, it is a list of things to beware of.

The list of behaviours and conditions was presented at the seminar to encourage discussion. After the seminar, the authors structured the list into four groups. Defensive behaviours are those of leaders and managers who use their positional power to stem the flow of information about specific risks or general shortcomings. Concealing behaviours are “softer” and “off-record” in the sense that, if challenged, the behaviours can be excused as attempts to reassure workers and promote a harmonious workplace for all. Corrupting behaviors are those that move workers’ norms away from valuing safety and taking personal responsibility for it. Lastly, the authors hypothesise that corrupting conditions make all of these behaviours more probable and are, in turn, reinforced by those behaviours.

One last conclusion is doubt about the extent to which contemporary safety management practices are designed to counter wilful blindness. For example, some models of risk assessment specify that a risk study should be independently

reviewed before the risk owners make their decision. Another example is the idea that investigative terms of reference should not be set unilaterally by the risk owner, but always multilaterally with the stakeholders and dynamically adjusted as new information comes to light. Perhaps the time is ripe for reviewing safety management practices, methods and processes, for their vulnerability to wilful blindness.

Detecting early warning signs of blindness

Authors: Frank Verschueren and Maria Luisa Villani

4.1 The concept and the claim

In earlier work done by the ESReDA project group Foresight in Safety, an early warning sign was defined as “an indicator of strengthening a hazard or of weakening a safety measure, which can result in an increase of frequency or severity of consequences of scenarios causing damage” [ESReDA 2020, p. 105].

In this interactive poster session we wanted to start from this definition and build further on it. Therefore, we propose that an early warning sign should be seen as the most early observed sign of disturbance or smaller disruption that when not acted on will escalate and can lead to major damage to people and other assets.

Our principal claim is that major accidents often occur because of a system’s inability to recognise and respond effectively to various (early) warning signs that arise during its functioning. A more positive formulation of our claim is that by optimising the detection of and actions on early warning signs, the risk of major accidents will be reduced.

This principal claim is accompanied by two insights which make our poster fit well in the subject of our Project Group, which is Risk and Knowledge Management. The first insight is that the use of early warning signs (EWS) is part of better Knowledge Management. Additionally, we argue that in a risk management context early warning signs are not “for free” and are directly linked with an obligation to analyse the new information, and to implement changes if the analysis shows that they are necessary. This leads to the second insight that the detection of EWS and consequently adequate acting upon them is essential to improve risk management.

As such, optimising the detection of early warning signs and an adequate acting on them drives an organisation towards a more effective and proactive “risk/knowledge” management.

We can reduce our blindness by defining early warning signs (EWS) and showing the impact of these EWS by developing corresponding escalation scenarios.

4.2 Facts and interpretation of cases

Accidents often happen as a result of failing to detect and handle EWS. Signals may be unnoticed when they arise, not be adequately amplified, or fail to clearly emerge in the process towards decision-making. They may even be disregarded by decision-makers, particularly after accidents occur, when defining investment plans for resilience improvement.

We start with the further development of our claim, i.e. that Early Warning Signs in our view are *not* innocent but are the most early observable disturbances of the process or system.

As such they are precursors in one or several escalating scenario’s leading to damage to people and assets. So, when EWS are not acted upon they escalate and accidents develop.

To recognise EWS, the organisation has to possess a clear view on the region of “normal”, “balanced” or “undisturbed” process/activity *and* its corresponding boundaries. These boundaries should be used as the triggers for the very first early warning signs. Passing or crossing such a boundary is a critical sign as it should warn the organisation/system that it has deviated from the normal way and that it is now operating in an abnormal, disturbed, disrupted or unsafe way. This is the beginning of an escalation meaning without action things even get worse.

The main factors contributing to their failure of detection include insufficient awareness of the critical parameters essential for the proper functioning of the processes or system, as well as the inability to identify the threshold at which monitoring these parameters transitions from normal to unsafe operation.

Thus, effective risk management requires knowing and monitoring all critical-relevant parameters, understanding the threshold up to which the escalation remains reversible — meaning the organisation still has time and resources to

intervene – and identifying the means which should be made available to stop and reverse the escalation.

4.3 Tracing the course of Early Warning Signs

In this context, sharing knowledge and experiences can help explore methods for detecting early warning signs in safety-critical systems to prevent accidents. In the interactive session, the Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (DIKW) pyramid [Rowley 2007] was introduced as a framework for discussing non-detection and suggesting methods of detection; hence, an illustration of the DIKW flow, expanded into a loop, was presented in the poster (see figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: The “Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom” by Rowley reproduced as a cycle to highlight the key drivers that facilitate the transition between each stage. Transitions that rely more heavily on human capabilities are in red (figure by Maria Luisa Villani).

The loop starts with methods for collecting data from reality and continues through the processing and interpretation of data to produce information. The transition from information to knowledge occurs through abstraction, internalisation, and the integration of new insights with pre-existing (tacit and explicit) knowledge, ultimately guiding decision-making towards some specific constrained objectives. Imagination and intelligence play a crucial role in this process, leading to actions that may reshape reality (i.e., improving the system’s transparency to risk and thereby improving the system resilience).

The session aimed to foster a discussion focused on identifying critical points that could disrupt this flow, especially the transition from knowledge to decision, potentially leading to blindness. Drawing insights from the Dali accident and participants’ other experiences, the session also sought to explore tools for recognising early warning signs and acting upon them, as well as tools for identifying blindness to such signs.

4.3.1 Examples of the Francis Scott Key Bridge case

Given that safety issues arise when moving from information to knowledge or, most often, from knowledge to decision, two examples from the Francis Scott Key Bridge case were used to highlight exemplary failures to take action(s) after clear signs. The first example concerns infrastructure and regulation upgrades after accidents. Knowledge of prior ship collisions should have prompted risk assessments for larger modern ships, but this was ignored in favour of focusing on other risks, such as terrorism.

We put forward that failure to adapt infrastructure for larger vessels was caused by a clear neglect of the following early warning signs: In 1980, a ship about one-third the size of the Dali lightly damaged a pier on the Francis Scott Key Bridge without more serious consequence. Still, despite this earlier incident, up to the bespoke actual accident no serious considerations were made to account for the possibility of collisions with much larger ships like the Dali, especially given the clear increased size of container vessels. In the same year 1980 there was the Sunshine Skyway Bridge accident in Florida (9th of May, 1980). This was a relevant early warning sign that should have raised awareness of this same type of risk. Shortly afterwards a study was published on ship-bridge collisions [MBC 1983]. At the time of the last accident (2024) this study was rather outdated and should have been better updated especially with respect to larger vessels.

A second example was the lack of investigation and information asymmetry in the power outages before the accident.

The Dali had experienced two power outages while docked in Baltimore, raising alarms about possible mechanical or electrical issues. However, these incidents didn’t serve as early warning signs and were not taken seriously enough to delay its departure or ensure it was fully operational before sailing. This involved a poor link between knowledge and decision-making. The ship’s power issues were a direct warning sign of potential danger, yet the decision to proceed with its departure showed a clear failure in risk management. There was yet another incident linked with the power supply. While undergoing routine engine maintenance on 23 March 2024, an alarm on the ship’s refrigerated containers went off while the ship was docked, likely due to an inconsistent power supply. This

event signalled a possible underlying issue with the ship's electrical or power systems, but it was also not addressed. The alarm was an indicator of inconsistent power, which should have raised concerns about the ship's overall electrical system, especially its reliability for future operations. After the alarm, there was no decision to delay the ship's departure from the port until the cause of the power issue was fully understood and resolved. The decision to allow the ship to continue its journey, despite the known alarm, shows a gap in translating available knowledge (power supply inconsistency) into risk mitigation (preventing the ship from sailing).

4.4 Results of the interactive session: claims, examples and questions

The information and thoughts brought forward by the participants can be grouped into comments about information management, knowledge management, and decision-making.

Comments concerning information management: Interpretation of signals was highlighted to be a critical link from data to information. Devices provide signals, but their value for more adequate decision-making depends on how effectively these signals are interpreted and acted upon. Blindness occurs not only when weak signals are ignored but also when misinterpretation arises from information overload, which can lead to a failure in reporting (e.g., alarm flooding). Furthermore, if the data is partial, incomplete, or influenced by biases, the conclusions drawn from it may be misleading, hindering the ability to detect warning signs or respond effectively to risks.

Methods of interpretation were said to be relevant as well. Of course, past scenarios analysis and causal inference are common tools to be applied to identify blindness. More interestingly, it was highlighted that blind spots might emerge when investigators prioritise verifying existing assumptions over falsifying them to uncover alternative explanations¹. Countering falsification is a critical part of scientific inquiry because it helps ensure that conclusions are not based solely on biased or incomplete perspectives. Promoting diversity in teams to gain multiple perspectives is a way to support the process of exploring alternative explanations, which aligns with the principle of countering falsification.

¹ Jens Rasmussen described this as the (sloppy) investigator's stop rule. "Keep investigating until you find a familiar cause to which you know the cure; then stop" [Rasmussen 1997]. It saves a lot of time, but at an unknown cost to safety.

Comments concerning knowledge management: Connected to the point above, the importance of including insights from various roles within an organisation, particularly those of shop-floor workers was highlighted. Examples included observing how employees develop their own methods or workarounds especially when standardised procedures do not fully address practical challenges. These adaptations are described as instances of the Efficiency-Thoroughness Trade-Off (ETTO), a concept by E. Hollnagel, which explains how people operate depending on situational demands and stress [Hollnagel 2009]. Fostering a culture of feedback and learning by understanding these workarounds and adaptations is crucial not only for investigating accidents but also for improving organisational resilience and knowledge management as a general practice. A further point of discussion was on the legal framework governing accident investigations and their prevention (a question from one participant was about possible updates). This included the obligations organisations have to produce detailed reports following accidents and the mechanisms in place to ensure compliance (e.g., safety distances). However, it was noticed that such obligations can vary across jurisdictions. It was agreed that regular and thorough inspections, when carried out effectively, play a crucial role in detecting early warning signs. Additionally, the discussion highlighted the importance of fostering a culture of vigilance through proactive monitoring and learning to ensure effective actions.

Comments concerning the decision-making step: Awareness without Action was identified as a missing link from knowledge to decision. While tools and processes to increase awareness may be in place, misaligned prioritisation of short-term savings over long-term risk mitigation is a sign of blindness. This becomes evident when companies wait for incidents elsewhere to serve as a wake-up call (e.g., the Dali accident should trigger EWS updates). Sometimes decisions are made but not implemented or postponed (missed link from decision to action). Continuous monitoring, quantification of the cost of inaction and benchmarking to compare organisational safety performance with peers were mentioned as tools to recognise early warning signs and support decision-making.

An insight related to this point was the tendency to dismiss low-probability events as unlikely, leaving them unaddressed until they escalate into big accidents. A societal perspective was suggested to address this issue, emphasising the need to recognise that risks cannot be entirely eliminated. Instead, society and organisations must focus on managing them responsibly. Concerning the capability to handle complex problems that often have interconnected causes extending beyond a single domain or department, it was noted that innovative ideas frequently originate from outside the organisation, particularly in cases where transformative changes need to be initiated.

4.5 Conclusions for safety

A preliminary conclusion for us is that improving the detection and treatment of early warning signs makes an organisation more resilient in a VUCA (Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, Ambiguous) context.

Most important is the fact that early detection of early warning signs accelerates the decision-making process so the organisation can cope with a higher volatility of disruptions. Accelerating the decision-making process also makes that the (re)actions can be smaller. And so, when the actions because of uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity would prove to be ill-directed with negative impact, they can be reversed with less damaging impact. [“Failing fast but safe and allowing early re-adaptation!”] Detecting early warning signs early on in the escalation process makes sure that risk/consequences are also addressed early on in the beginning of their escalation with a smaller (up to negligible) damaging impact. Furthermore, an organisation that is engaged in proactive action will have stronger motivated employees because they feel that their efforts are improving every one’s health and safety and contributing to the organisation’s resilience.

By optimising the detection of early warning signs and their adequate treatment, an organisation will arrive at a state of higher vigilance and alertness. This will reduce our blindness and more specifically the risk of major accidents.

The optimisation of early warning signs detection and their adequate treatment adds four powerful accompanying organisational aspects that drive the organisation towards this safety state of higher vigilance and alertness. The first accompanying organisational aspect is higher agility: the increased ability to quickly adapt safety strategies to unexpected disruptions of the safety situation. A second accompanying organisational aspect is higher flexibility: the increased ability to adjust processes structures and policies to respond to the variety of disruptions of the safety situation. A third accompanying organisational aspect is higher proactivity of Risk Management: the increased ability to identify potential safety risks early enough to mitigate them before escalation. The fourth accompanying organisational aspect is the more Data-driven extent of the organisational decision-making: Utilising data-analytics to feed safety strategies and make informed evidence-based safety decisions.

Smarter communication to tackle blindness

Author: Peter Kouwenhoven

5.1 The concept and the claim

According to Trevor Kletz, “accidents are not caused by lack of knowledge, but by a failure to use the knowledge that is available” [Kletz 2001]. There are two problems concerning the application of available knowledge. First, knowledge is domain-dependent: if matters become complex and one has to consider too many aspects, a decision-maker will focus on his field of expertise and omit the other considerations included in the risk analysis. Two other phenomena that make it difficult to revoke an earlier decision are confirmation bias (the tendency to interpret and remember information that confirms a prior belief) and inconsistency avoidance (the tendency to resist any change in a conclusion, even when new information suggest another decision) [Kappes et al. 2020; Rudorf et al. 2014].

Our short-term working memory has limited capacity; on average 7 items can be retrieved. This means too much competing information will lead to a selection, and most of the time this will be biased towards one’s own field of expertise. These aspects will be deepened further, and others will fade to the background.

In addition, confirmation bias is well known as the tendency to hear only information that confirms one’s beliefs. Another property of confirmation bias is less well known: the resistance to reverse an earlier decision, even when new information contradicts the one the prior decision is based on.

In this fourth Athens seminar poster we claimed that accidents are due to bad communication of the risk that is *de facto* understood by the safety professional

but not by the decision-maker who remains blind to the risks (domain dependency). In addition, decision-makers may have a motivational blindness if they decided otherwise earlier about the case (inconsistency avoidance). The problem is thus not the lack of knowledge in the organisation, but the failure to communicate the case to the target audience in such a way that a layman understands the meaning of the message and is invited to act on it.

As perceptions of hazards differ from person to person, especially when raised by another discipline, the message is sent and received, yet it may not lead to change. To drive change, safety professionals should tailor the message to match the perception of the audience: to concentrate on the potential and probability of financial loss when in discussion with accountants, on governance issues when in discussion with administrators, and on technological issues when discussing with engineers. At the same time, both the person sharing the information and the person receiving it need to understand that effort is needed to shift beliefs and gain understanding. Sharing knowledge is not the same as learning from knowledge!

5.2 Results of the interactive session: claims, examples and questions

The keys to smarter communication were discussed at the seminar. The input of the audience, was then categorised into seven viewpoints that may be utilised to deliver a message:

1. What is the content of the communication?
2. What is the best method of communication?
3. What is the evidence used in the communication?
4. What is the objective of the communication?
5. What is the best timing to communicate the issue(s)?
6. Who are the target group(s) of the communication?
7. Who should communicate the issues?

The suggestions given in table 5.1 include the input of the audience together with the thoughts of the presenter of the fourth poster. They should not be read as a guide on how to write intrusive reports nor are they intended to be definitive statements on the issues. Instead, they are ideas to think about, some of which may be found useful in some situations, others in other situations.

Content	The content should contain the identified hazard and its possible consequences, the likelihood of the hazard to occur, its most probable scenario and the worst-case scenario. Next, an overview of the consequences for specific stakeholders shall be given (fatalities, financial loss, political impact, influence on administration, effects on institutions, reputation, lost revenues for the Baltimore port, and so on). Finally, the report should contain an invitation to take action.
Method	The identified hazard should stand out of all other reported issues that compete for the attention of administrators. A standalone report shall be focused to the target group, the decision makers within the administrative institutions.
Evidence	Evidence to support the reported probabilities and estimated consequences can be given by engineering studies, model simulations, prototype experiments, historical data on similar accidents and data on the occurrence of precursors.
Objective	To start an open discussion without any prejudice. The discussion will provide a complete picture of the views the stakeholders involved hold. The objective of the discussion shall be to convince the (board of) decision-maker(s) to take appropriate action. When resistance is encountered, it is advised to postpone a decision to prevent motivational blindness.
Timing	Minutes of meeting may draw attention to an identified hazard and a future study to be submitted concerning the potentially major consequences. Don't send the report alongside other reports related to the meeting. Next, don't send the report in times when important issues compete for the attention of directors and administrators (political turmoil, upcoming elections or vacation season).
Target groups	As mentioned above, the obvious stakeholders in the Francis Scott Key Bridge case are directors and administrators of institutions taking care of transport (Maryland Port Administration, Maryland Department of Transportation, Baltimore Harbour Safety and Coordination Committee, Harbour pilots, Road Authorities, US Coast Guard – sector Maryland, shipowners and-so-on). All have responsibilities towards their employees and the public, have financial interests and the possible impact on production processes when supply chains are obstructed.
Who shall report?	It is unlikely that, when the hazard may lead to multiple fatalities or entering heavy financial obligations, one single person decides. Rather a Board of Directors or a Supervisory Board will jointly take far-reaching decisions. Preferably the report warning for the identified hazard will be drafted by a committee that mimics the composition of the Board. That is, the sections of the report are written by authors of similar discipline (financial-, political-, and legal experts, risk analysts, construction engineers, and marine architects).

Table 5.1: Suggestions for communicating the need for a safety-related investment to decision-makers.

The audience who participated in the interactive session felt that it would be productive to gather together with people from various disciplines to discuss the issues, and that writing the proposal together would bring credibility to the issues.

In the case of the Francis Scott Key Bridge accident, some elements of imperfect communication can be identified. For example, the risk was addressed in the minutes of the annual meetings [Thompson and Duncan 2024], which means that it was not a statement that stood out from other issues. It is also unclear who received the minutes: the participants of the meeting only, or also others who played a role in the safety of the bridge. When no action was taken, the message was not escalated to a higher level. It is also unclear if engineering studies were made; a possible response as it concerns the evaluation of safety, financial and societal impact. It looks like the decision was already taken not to investigate the warnings given [Thompson and Duncan 2024].

5.3 Conclusions for safety

When analysing accident cases, in hindsight it is easy to identify communication failures, but that doesn't enhance safety. Poor communication is not easy to identify proactively, but one can try to avoid inadequate communication using a strategy: look into what you want to achieve, on how to identify and further reduce unmanaged risks, and to understand what a specific problem indicates. Discourse is important: does the sender know what the decision-maker needs? There should be discussions, networking, conversations: without trust, there will be no listening. Building a relationship is paramount for the exchange of concerns. Communication on various subjects today will pave the way for a deeper discussion tomorrow. If too much information is presented, the decision-maker will tend to stick to their own field of expertise and overlook other information. Special attention is required to address risks in small and medium-sized enterprises. Both the decision-makers (Board of Directors) and HSE specialists have difficulty accessing expert support.

Summarising the output of the seminar interactive session, a good starting point would probably be to look at the message from the viewpoint of the decision-maker. What does she/he need to know to manage the risk?

Conclusion

Paradoxically, although blindness to risk is widespread, discussion of it is taboo in the workplace. Avoiding and correcting for blindness depends on finding ways to make it discussible.

The seminar provided insights into the how and why their warnings have been ignored. Before these insights were obtained, the lack of (appropriate) action was simply attributed to poor judgement of the responsible directors. Equipped with the insights given, safety professionals can look for the reasons behind, and direct their efforts to convincing the decision-makers to take action on their warnings.

A pragmatic way is the use of the early precursors of escalation scenarios as early warning signs which are followed by a decision to act or not to act. The effect of not making a decision nor to act should be made clear through a link of the EWS (as precursor of a specific escalation scenario) and the worse final consequence of the same specific escalation scenario. This brings forward a need for specific escalation scenarios as we already highlighted in a previous document [ESReDA 2020].

Organisational blindness to safety risks is a perhaps inevitable outcome of the conflict between our collective desire for the kinds of goods or services that can only be provided by complex and high-hazard facilities or infrastructures, our unwillingness to pay the high costs that would be required to design and operate these systems at very high levels of safety, and our desire to hold individuals responsible for the failures and accidents that inevitably arise. Indeed, as industrial and technological systems become more reliable due to our improved knowledge of their risks, accidents become both more exceptional and less socially acceptable. If leaders of such organisations are conscientious in analysing all the risks associated with the activity, they will be obliged to accept certain risks (risk elimination being impossible for both practical and economic reasons), and carefully document this acceptance, which will be held against them in case an accident arises. These leaders have a clear incentive to remain ignorant concerning safety risks, in order to avoid liability. As noted by organisational scholar Brunsson ([Brunsson 2002], mentioned in chapter 3), many forms

of organised hypocrisy are used in order to cope with the tension between these conflicting objectives, and some amount of deceit or lying is necessary for social cohesion [Hayes et al. 2024].

The Francis Scott Key Bridge accident is a good illustration of critical infrastructures whose management involves different owners, operators, regulators (for land-based traffic safety, for maritime safety, for the prevention of terrorism), professional groups such as marine pilots, and users. These complex multi-stakeholder systems are put in place in the name of participatory governance, which embodies democratic principles and often improves effectiveness. Unfortunately, the associated organisational complexity must be carefully managed to limit its impact on accountability for safety, the ownership of responsibility for safety, and the ability to make decisions related to engineering upgrades that will inevitably cause pain to some stakeholders.

Blindness to risk can be considered at the level of the individual, often involving structures. The relevant structures are diverse. For example: measurement systems that exclude certain facts, or pool them into meaningless statistics, can become institutionalised; monocultures, whether professional or demographic, amongst decision-makers can exclude other perspectives; problems of accountability can reward decision-makers for blindness to risks and motivate them to perpetuate blindness.

In the context of a VUCA world, the imperative to address organisational blindness to safety risks becomes even more pressing. The volatility and uncertainty of modern business environments can make it difficult for organisations to anticipate and prepare for potential risks. Furthermore, the complexity of modern organisations and systems can create a multitude of potential failure points, making it challenging to identify and mitigate risks.

To navigate this complex and dynamic landscape, organisations must adopt a proactive and adaptive approach to risk management, one that prioritises transparency, accountability, and diversity of perspectives. This requires a fundamental shift in organisational culture, from one that rewards risk avoidance and ignorance to one that encourages open discussion, experimentation, and learning from failure. By embracing this new paradigm, organisations can develop the resilience and agility needed to thrive in a VUCA world, where the ability to anticipate and respond to emerging risks is a key determinant of success.

Globalisation of business also creates special conditions for blindness, as risks are often transferred to remote locations or borne by people who are not directly involved in the production or consumption of goods and services. Thus, the risks of producing goods and services enjoyed by one group of people may be borne out-of-sight and out-of-mind by another group. This can lead to lack of awareness

and accountability, making it even more challenging to address organisational blindness to safety risks. Also, the interconnectedness of organisations means that locally unseen risks can be globally manifested. Thinking global but acting local is a challenge for governance.

Ultimately, the effective management of safety risks in a VUCA world demands a deep understanding of the complex interplay between organisational, social and technological factors and a commitment to ongoing learning, enhancing innovation, and continuing improvement.

The seminar investigated the forms of blindness that may play a role in the absence of decisions. To have the safety professional set priorities, he would have to know which type of blindness occurs most often and what strategy combats inactivity best. It is recommended to:

1. do research into the frequency which type of blindness is causing the lack of action.
2. do some empirical research into the successes of various strategies to combat inactivity.

Writing this paper has also brought up questions of definition. What is blindness to risk, and what are its forms? Progress is faster, usually, when similar things are studied together and when the relationships between underlying factors are made explicit. A taxonomy of blindness to risk is needed, most likely one based on study of the phenomena that create it.

Although a small segment of the workforce, safety professionals have a significant role in foresight and countering blindness. As well as pointing out issues missing from a business case, they assure the safety management processes of their organisations. These processes (e.g. risk assessment) can become denatured over time and require maintenance – their correct functioning cannot be taken for granted.

What organisational role the safety profession sees for itself is a moot point. Its star, as it were, was ascendant in the 1970s. Legislative developments; funding; academic, technical and scientific efforts; all encouraged a vigorous, professional approach to revealing and managing safety risks. Over fifty years, in many helpful ways, safety management has gone from breakthrough to routine. At the same time, the role of the safety professional has moved from an empowered advocate to a compliance manager who has symbolic guardianship of safety. How do contemporary safety professionals help their employers avoid and correct blindness to risk, and could they do more?

A decision-maker's blindness to risks persists until displaced by better knowledge. Often this knowledge is provided by more junior people in the organisation. However, people self-censor when they lack agency or security. The suppression can be structural, but it can also reflect weak skills for evidencing and voicing concerns. Leadership has its place, but organisations need to consider fostering lifelong learning in the workforce, particularly the "informal" type that deals with skills of communication, problem-solving, networking, and learning how to learn. They also need to recognise that certain behaviours or attitudes which are often considered socially undesirable (highlighting points where individual or collective performance is inadequate, not allowing inconvenient facts to be "swept under the carpet", reminding people of commitments they made, criticising decisions that are detrimental to safety, etc.) are required for continued safe operation. The encouragement of these behaviours and attitudes ("speaking up", assertiveness) should be embedded in the organisational culture.

Organisational blindness to risks has patterns, and understanding these is the key to improving timely management of risks. At the moment, retribution and blame obscure the patterns to a great extent. There is very likely to be value in harnessing new technology as well as reinvigorating known techniques to manage risk. However, the problem is social, not just technical, and to gain traction we must find ways to make a taboo subject discussible and susceptible to improvement.

There is, of course, a place for justice and retribution in human affairs. However, prevention needs researchers and practitioners to understand the causes of blindness to risk and provide *liberating alternatives* that lead to foresight and timely management of risks.

Bibliography

- Allyn International (2024). The evolution of container ships and their sizes—largest container ships. Accessed 7 April 2025. Available at <https://logisticselearning.com/largest-container-ships/>.
- Argyris, C. (1988). Problems in producing usable knowledge for implementing liberating alternatives. In Bell, D., Raiffa, H., and Tversky, A., Ed., *Decision making: descriptive, normative and prescriptive interactions*. Cambridge University Press.
- Argyris, C. (1994). Good communication that blocks learning. *Harvard Business Review*, 72(4):77–85.
- Argyris, C. (1999). *On Organisational Learning*. Blackwell. ISBN: 978-0631213093, 480 pages.
- Argyris, C. and Schön, D. A. (1978). *Organizational learning: a theory of action perspective*. Addison Wesley, Reading, MA, USA. ISBN: 978-0201001747, 356 pages.
- Bennett, N. and Lemoine, G. J. (2014). What a difference a word makes: Understanding threats to performance in a VUCA world. *Business Horizons*, 57(3):311–317. DOI: 10.1016/j.bushor.2014.01.001.
- Brunsson, N. (2002). *The Organization of Hypocrisy: Talk, Decisions and Actions in Organizations*. Copenhagen Business School Press. ISBN: 978-8763001069.
- Cyert, R. M. and March, J. G. (1963). *A behavioural theory of the firm*. Blackwell, Cambridge, MA, USA. ISBN: 978-0631174516, 268 pages.
- Dalton, M. (1959). *Men who manage: Fusions of feeling and theory in administration*. Wiley. ISBN: 978-0471191407, 318 pages.
- ESReDA (2020). Enhancing safety: The challenge of foresight. Technical report, ESReDA, Luxembourg. DOI: 10.2760/382517.
- Festinger, L. (1957). *A theory of cognitive dissonance*. Stanford University Press. ISBN: 978-0804701310, 291 pages.
- Founders Workshop (2024). Breaking down knowledge silos: Strategies for enhanced team collaboration. Accessed 02/11/2024. Available at <https://foundersworkshop.com/blog/organizational-culture/breaking-down-knowledge-silos-strategies-for-enhanced-team-collaboration/>.
- Garforth, A., Kingston, J., and Scheffers, P. (2018). Are structural weaknesses limiting the capacity to learn from incidents? In *Accident Investigation and Learning to Improve Safety Management in Complex Systems: Remaining Challenges. Proceedings of the 55th ESReDA Seminar, Bucharest, Romania, 9–10 October 2018*. Agenția de Investigare Feroviară Română - AGIFER.
- Hayes, J., Maslen, S., Holdsworth, S., and Sandri, O. (2021). Defining the capable engineer: Non-technical skills that support safe decisions in uncertain, dynamic situations. *Safety Science*, 141. DOI: 10.1016/j.ssci.2021.105324.
- Hayes, J., Maslen, S., and Schulman, P. R. (2024). A case of collective lying: How deceit becomes entrenched in organizational safety behavior. *Safety Science*, 176. DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.4672959.
- Heffernan, M. (2011). *Willful Blindness: Why We Ignore the Obvious at our Peril*. Random House. ISBN: 978-0802719980.
- Hollnagel, E. (2009). *The ETTO Principle: Efficiency-Thoroughness Trade-Off: Why Things That Go Right Sometimes Go Wrong*. CRC Press. ISBN: 978-1315616247, 162 pages.
- Jackall, R. (1988). *Moral Mazes: The World of Corporate Managers*. Oxford University Press. ISBN: 978-0195060805, 249 pages.
- Kappes, A., Harvey, A., Lohrenz, T., Montague, R., and Sharot, T. (2020). Confirmation bias in the utilization of others' opinion strength. *Nature Neuroscience*, 23(1):130–137. DOI: 10.1038/s41593-019-0549-2.
- Kingston, J. and Dien, Y. (2020). The McNamara fallacy and the fog of foresight at work. *Health and Safety Bulletin*, 489:11–16.
- Kletz, T. A. (2001). *Learning from Accidents*. Routledge. ISBN: 978-0080510064, 352 pages.
- Lessig, L. (2011). *Republic, lost: How money corrupts Congress – and a plan to stop it*. 400 pages.
- Luban, D. (1999). Contrived ignorance. *The Georgetown Law Journal*, 87(4):957–980. Available at <https://scholarship.law.georgetown.edu/facpub/1751/>.
- Maslen, S., Hayes, J., Holdsworth, S., and Sandri, O. (2021). When ethics is a technical matter: Engineers' strategic appeal to ethical considerations in advocating for system integrity. *Science and engineering ethics*, 27(4). DOI: 10.1007/s11948-021-00324-7.
- MBC (1983). Ship collisions with bridges: The nature of the accidents, their prevention and mitigation. Technical report, US National Research Council. Committee on Ship-Bridge Collisions, Marine Board, Commission on Engineering and Technical Systems. Available at <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/tr/pdf/ADA135602.pdf>.
- Moore-Bick, M., Akbor, A., and Istephan, T. (2024). Report of the public inquiry into the fire at grenfell tower on 14 june 2017 – executive summary. Technical report, Grenfell Tower Inquiry. Available at <https://www.grenfelltowerinquiry.org.uk/phase-2-report>.
- Morrison, E. W. and Milliken, F. J. (2000). Organizational silence: A barrier to change and development in a pluralistic world. *Academy of Management Review*, 25(4):706–725. DOI: 10.5465/AMR.2000.3707697.
- Nader, R. (2016). Acceptance speech to the “automotive hall of fame”. Available at <https://youtu.be/vSYZnImEkys>.
- NRI (2009). Management oversight and risk tree users manual. Technical report, Noordwijk Risk Initiative Foundation, The Netherlands. Available at <https://www.nri.eu.com/NRI1.pdf>.
- NRI (2014). Events and conditional factors analysis. Technical report, Noordwijk Risk Initiative Foundation, The Netherlands. Available at <https://www.nri.eu.com/NRI4.pdf>.
- Rasmussen, J. (1997). Risk management in a dynamic society: a modelling problem. *Safety Science*, 27(2):183–213. DOI: 10.1016/S0925-7535(97)00052-0.
- Rowley, J. (2007). The wisdom hierarchy: Representations of the DIKW hierarchy. *Journal of Information Science*, 33(2):163–180. DOI: 10.1177/0165551506070706.
- Rudorf, S., Weber, B., and Kuhnen, C. (2014). Stock ownership and learning from financial information. In *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Society for Neuroeconomics, sept 2014, Miami*.
- Shaw, W. H. and Barry, V. (1989). *Moral Issues in Business*. Wadsworth Pub. Co. ISBN: 978-0534097863, 542 pages.
- Snook, S. A. (2000). *Friendly fire: The accidental shootdown of US Black Hawks over Northern Iraq*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, USA. ISBN: 978-0691095189, 280 pages.
- Soraghan, M. (2010). Companies involved in Gulf oil spill play 'name that disaster' with eye on posterity. September 9, 2010. Available at <https://archive.nytimes.com/www.nytimes.com/gwire/2010/09/09/09greenwire-companies-involved-in-gulf-oil-spill-play-name-79834.html>.

- Souarez, A. (2018). How to combat executive detachment and achieve great team results. Accessed on 02/11/2024. Available at <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/how-combat-executive-detachment-achieve-great-team-results-souarez/>.
- Sull, D. (2009). *The Upside of Turbulence: Seizing Opportunity in an Uncertain World*. HarperCollins Business. ISBN: 978-0061771156.
- Thompson, S. and Duncan, I. (2024). Long before key bridge collapse, Baltimore mariners warned of 'ship strikes'. *Washington Post*. Friday May 24 2024. Available at <https://www.washingtonpost.com/investigations/2024/05/23/key-bridge-warnings-ship-strikes/>.
- Vaughan, D. (1996). *The Challenger launch decision: Risky technology, culture and deviance at NASA*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago. ISBN: 978-0226851754.

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